

Action of Raney Nickel on Steroids and Terpenoids in High Boiling Solvents

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DURING my association with Sir Robert Robinson at the Dyson Perrins Laboratory, Oxford, we,^{1,2} carried out an interesting study on the action of the catalyst Raney nickel on the strychnos bases in boiling xylene solution. Under these conditions strychnine gave neostrychnine by a shifting of the isolated double bond one step nearer to the basic nitrogen, i. e. from 21 (22) to 20-position. In this way, strychnidine gave neostrychnidine, brucine gave neobrucine and brucidine gave neobrucidine. At Calcutta, working on steroids, I became interested in this reaction and undertook an investigation on the action of Raney nickel on a large number of steroids in high boiling solvents. In view of the results obtained, the studies were extended to a large number of triterpenoids also.

As available from a special report, Ruschig (cf. Kleiderer³) carried out the catalytic conversion of pregnenolone to progesterone in presence of Raney nickel with cyclohexanone as a hydrogen acceptor. Kleiderer and Kornfeld⁴ determined the general applicability of this oxidation and also studied the possibility of using it in the reverse sense, i. e. as a reductive method in presence of a hydrogen donor, more or less similar to the use of aluminium alkoxides. A number of secondary alcohols, e. g. cholesterol and cholestanol were oxidised to the related ketones, Δ^4 -cholestenone and cholestanone respectively with Raney nickel in presence of cyclohexanone as a hydrogen acceptor. For catalytic reductions they used various types of hydrogen donors like ethanol, isopropanol and cyclohexanol. Subsequently Romo⁵ prepared a number of 3-keto- Δ^4 -steroids by oxidation of 3-hydroxy- Δ^4 -steroids with Raney nickel in presence of acetone or methyl ethyl ketone as the hydrogen acceptor. According to a patent taken out by Sondheimer and his associates⁶ steroids containing a double bond, α : β - to a secondary alcoholic group, on treatment with Raney nickel and a hydrogen acceptor like acetone are oxidised, the secondary alcoholic group being converted into a ketonic group.

It is important to note that in all the above cases involving oxidation/reduction with Raney nickel a hydrogen acceptor/donor was invariably used, whereas in the conversion of the strychnos bases into the neoisomers one part of the molecule acts as the acceptor and another part as the donor and no separate reagent is necessary for any such purpose. Along this line an investigation was taken up by us⁷⁻¹¹ on the action of Raney nickel on steroids avoiding use of a separate reagent as hydrogen acceptor/donor. In the first instance, we carried out the reaction in boiling xylene, as in the case of the strychnos bases, with diosgenin as the steroid, but most of the diosgenin was recovered unchanged. The reaction thus appeared to be very slow at the

temperature of boiling xylene. Accordingly, the reaction was repeated in *p*-cymene solution under boiling condition. The product isolated in this case was Δ^4 tigogenone. In a similar manner stigmasterol gave $\Delta^4, 2^2$ -stigmastadine-3-one, tigogenin gave tigogenone and hecogenin gave hecogenone.

Using large excess of the catalyst, however, under the same conditions diosgenin gave tigogenone with saturation of the double bond. Similarly, stigmasterol gave $\Delta^{2,2}$ -stigmasten-3-one and β -sitosterol gave sitostanone. The case of cholesterol was studied more exhaustively. In this case the normal product was Δ^4 -cholestenone. With excess of the catalyst the major product was cholestanone, whereas with very large excess of the catalyst a dimer was obtained. From a study of their, nmr and mass spectra of this dimer, its identity with the dimer of Corey and Young^{1,2} was established. The dimer was also obtained starting from cholestanol using a very large excess of the catalyst. With very large excess of the catalyst, the dimer is the only product that could be isolated.

It was observed that in these reactions where there was a saturation of 5 : 6-double bond, the configuration of A/B ring fusion of the products isolated was invariably *trans*. To confirm this finding regarding the stereospecificity of the effect of Raney nickel in high boiling solvents, steroids having *cis* configuration in A/B ring fusion were subjected to the above reaction with Raney nickel. Thus smilagenone, when heated under reflux condition with Raney nickel, in *p*-cymene solution gave tigogenone having A/B *trans* configuration with 5 α -H in place of 5 β -H. Tigogenone was also obtained in a similar manner from epismilagenin. Under similar manner coprostanone gave cholestanone and sarsasapogenin gave neotigogenone. The action of Raney nickel on cholic acid in boiling *p*-cymene appeared to be rather complex. Methyl cholate, however, gave a small yield of methyl 7 α , 12 α -dihydroxy-3-oxo-5 α -cholanoate under similar experimental conditions (cf. Danielsson¹³; Ziller, Mitra and Elliot¹⁴; Mitra and Elliot¹⁵). In all these cases a 5 β -steroid is converted into 5 α -steroid.

The androgenic activity of 5 β -androstanones are much weaker than that of the 5 α -isomers. In this respect it is interesting to note that in a similar manner the biologically inactive 3 α -hydroxyetiocholan-17-one, 3 β -hydroxyetiocholan-17-one and etiocholan-3, 17-dione were all smoothly converted into androstan-3, 17-dione having considerable androgenic activity.

We also observed¹⁶ that yuccagenin, having two secondary hydroxyl groups in 2 α - and 3 β -positions respectively, under similar conditions gives tigogenone.

It seems that it first transforms into the 5 : 6-dihydro-2 α -hydroxy-3-keto compound and the latter by allylic fission loses the 2 α -hydroxy group and forms tigogenone. In conformity with this it was observed that both gitogenin and 3-dehydrogitogenin also yield tigogenone under these conditions.

In place of *p*-cymene (b.p. 177°) other similar high boiling solvents, e. g. pseudocumene (b. p. 168°) may be used, but in such a case, at the lower temperature the saturation of the 5 : 6-double bond becomes difficult, in other words in boiling pseudocumene cholesterol yields Δ^4 -cholestenone but not cholestanone.

The effect of Raney nickel on steroids in boiling *p*-cymene solution thus involves five different types of reactions as summarised below :

Type A — Dehydrogenation (oxidation) of the 3 α - or 3 β -OH group ;

Type B — Hydrogenation of 5 : 6-double bond ;

Type C — Isomerization of 5 β -hydrogen to 5 α -(i. e. *cis*-A/B to *trans*-A/B) ;

Type D — Dimerization ;

Type E — Allylic fission.

The reaction was extended to a number of triterpenes¹⁷⁻¹⁸. α -Amyrin on refluxing with Raney nickel in *p*-cymene solution gave α -amyrone. Similarly, β -amyrin gave β -amyrone and taraxerol gave taraxerone. But lupeol gave lupanone with saturation of the double bond. In this case, with smaller amount of catalyst, instead of formation of lupenone considerable amount of lupeol was recovered unchanged. Lupanone was also obtained from the saturated alcohol, dihydrolupeol in a similar manner.

The action of Raney nickel on ursolic acid and betulinic acid appeared to be rather complex, but methyl ursolate gave methyl ursonate and methylbetulate gave the saturated keto-ester, methyl dihydrobetulonate. Epifriedelinol, a saturated pentacyclic triterpene alcohol, when refluxed with Raney nickel in *p*-cymene solution afforded friedelin and germanicol on similar treatment afforded germanicone.

When cycloartenol was heated with a small amount of the catalyst in *p*-cymene solution, besides a small amount of the saturated ketone, cycloartanone, two isomeric unsaturated ketones were obtained, cycloartenone and a new ketone isocycloartenone. The last one is believed to be formed by a free radical mechanism, first knocking out an allylic hydrogen atom which then adds to the olefinic carbon. It was converted into the corresponding alcohol, isocycloartenol, and the latter on treatment with Raney nickel catalyst in boiling *p*-cymene yielded a mixture of cycloartenone, isocycloartenone and cycloartanone. When cycloartenol (a 3 β -alcohol) was heated with an excess of the catalyst in a similar manner, the product obtained was the saturated ketone, cycloartanone. Cycloarten-3 α -ol when heated with moderately large amount of Raney nickel in *p*-cymene solution also yielded the saturated ketone, cycloartanone. When

$\Delta^{9(11)}$ lanostenol was heated with the catalyst in a similar manner the product was $\Delta^{9(11)}$ -lanostenone irrespective of the amount of catalyst used. Lupeol hydrochloride under similar conditions gave a ketone, 18-iso- β -amyranone. The latter product was also obtained when the reaction was carried out with 18-iso- β -amyranol. From this it is evident that under the conditions Raney nickel may bring about hydrogenolysis of triterpene chlorides.

In line with the observations in the cases of yuccagenin, gitogenin and dehydrogitogenin¹⁶, it was observed¹⁹ that gymnemagenin loses four oxygen atoms out of six hydroxy groups as also two carbon atoms. The allylic type fission thus appears to be operative in this case also. Moreover, this example also indicates that a hydroxy group in 22-position is also suitable for dehydrogenation by this method with formation of a keto group. Also²⁰ under these conditions erythrodiol, uvaol and betulin yield olean- Δ^{12} -28n-al-3-one, urs- Δ^{12} -28-al-3-one and lupan-28-al-3-one respectively. In these three cases besides the usual change at the 3-position, the primary hydroxyl group at the 28-position is dehydrogenated to an aldehyde group.

The effect of Raney nickel on triterpenoids in boiling *p*-cymene solution thus mainly involves the following four types of reactions.

Type I Dehydrogenation (oxidation) of the 3 α - or 3 β -OH group and of OH group at 22- and 28-positions ;

Type II Saturation of the easily reducible double bond ;

Type III Shifting of the double bond to an adjacent position as in an allylic shift,

Type IV Allylic fission.

The Raney nickel reaction appears essentially to be a hydrogenation cum dehydrogenation process. When conjugated steroid ketone like cholest-4-en-3-one was heated with Raney Ni in *p*-cymene no reduction of the double bond took place and the ketone could be recovered unchanged. It was thought that the double bond in conjugation with the carbonyl group might have resisted the hydrogenation under the conditions. Hence the reaction was carried out with a few triterpene ketones with easily reducible isolated double bond like cycloartenone, lupenone, methyl ketobetulate, etc. In these cases also no saturation of the double bond occurred and the ketones were recovered unchanged. Even unsaturated acetates like cholesteryl acetate and cycloartenyl acetate were unaffected by this reaction. But unsaturated 3-hydroxy steroids or terpenoids, smoothly furnished the saturated ketones on treatment with Raney Ni in boiling *p*-cymene solution. Thus the hydrogen necessary for the reduction of the double bond appears to be supplied from the reacting molecules and not necessarily from the Raney Ni itself. The hydrogen evolved on dehydrogenation of the alcohols actually brings about the saturation of the double bond in presence of the catalyst. The solvent may perhaps consume some amount of this liberated hydrogen.

The fact that for the formation of a saturated ketone larger amount of the catalyst is necessary, seems to suggest that with the increase in the amount of the catalyst, the availability of the surface, where reduction of the double bond with the liberated hydrogen takes place, increases—thus increasing the availability of the gas for reduction of the dehydrogenated product, the unsaturated ketone, on the surface of the catalyst. These hold good in the case of steroids also.

One interesting point to note in this connection is that triterpene alcohols with a reducible bond on heating with Raney Ni in *p*-cymene yield in most cases the saturated ketone, whilst in the case of sterols with 5:6-double bond both unsaturated and saturated ketones are obtained. Dehydrogenation of 3-hydroxy group of steroids having 5:6-double bond promotes a shift of the double bond to 4:5 position. Whereas in the case of triterpenes, hydrogenation of the isolated double bond is much easier than that of the 3-keto conjugated double bond of steroid ketones.

Lastly, I may mention that we also carried out this reaction in the absence of any solvent by heating the compound with Raney nickel to the desired temperature under controlled conditions in an inert (also hydrogen) atmosphere²¹ with proper safety measures. The results in the few case studied are of the same type, though the yields are poor.

Recently²¹ the reaction was extended to simple saturated mono-cyclic systems. For example, 1-menthol furnished 1-menthone in the usual way. An interesting case was observed in the case of cyclohexan-1:2-dione. When this was heated with Raney nickel in *p*-cymene it gave cyclohexan-1:2-diol and a small amount of a dimer of cyclohexan-2-ol-1-one.

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